

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SUPER-BLACK SURFACE COATING USING CARBON NANOMATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Super-black material absorbs almost all light that falls on it, because little light can be transmitted or reflected. With this unique property, super-black material can be applied to many fields, such as optical sensor, solar energy absorber, black body calibration and so on. Especially, optical baffles with super-black surface is critical to suppress the stray light for the detectors of the satellites [1]. Hence, various process and materials have been developed to blacken the surface by chemical treatment [2], plating [3] and painting [4]. Meanwhile, most researches fabricated the super-black surface on a small scale in laboratory, rather than ones with high performance in practical application. This paper provided an efficient and cost-effective approach to achieve a super-black surface by combining spray coating of carbon nanocomposite with periodic micro surface structure.

Carbon is a good absorber because of the π -band's optical transitions [5], so carbon nanotube (CNT) solution was sprayed on the Cu or PI substrate to enhance light absorption. Polymers and dispersant were also added into the coating to increase adhesion and uniformity. Total reflectance of as-prepared carbon nanocomposite coating is less than 8% in visible region (as shown in Fig.1 (a)). Yet the absorption was limited because of the moderate reflection at the air-dielectric interface. Therefore, conical periodic micro structure was processed on the coating surface to form a gradual change of effective refractive indices between air-dielectric interface.

Figure 1: Laser engraving system to prepare micro structure.

A CO₂ laser engraving system was employed to prepare the micro structure (as shown in Fig.1). Through changing the laser path and power, conical periodic structure with an average height about 5 μ m and interval length of 100 μ m was prepared successfully (as shown in Fig.1 (b)). Total reflectance of the as-prepared coating decreased to 3% in visible region, 47% lower than that of the unprocessed coating. This laser texturing method has high efficiency and can be applied to different surface shapes. Combined flexible spray-coating method with effective laser surface texturing process, this surface coating has good adaptability as well as high light absorption performance in practical application.

Figure 2: (a) total reflectance of CNT coating before and after laser texturing; (b) surface morphology of conical periodic structure by laser confocal microscope.

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